

Learning Youth Through Knowledge Advancement (LYKA): A Comprehensive Product for Developing Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips to Enhance Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

Quality education significantly impacts a student's future through knowledge, skills, and values. However, the Philippines is now experiencing a learning crisis and learning loss that hinders students to achieve their full potential as reflected in PISA 2022. As part of this, a new curriculum also known as MATATAG Curriculum was launched by DepEd in 2023 and implemented in S.Y. 2024-2025 which aims to address challenges in education.

In the MATATAG curriculum, specifically in grade 7, teachers are using lesson exemplars as instructional materials. Thus, one of the challenges expressed by the teachers in implementing the MATATAG curriculum was insufficient instructional materials for teachers and inappropriate learning materials for students. Hence, as instructional materials, LYKA (Learning Youth through Knowledge and Advancement) lesson exemplars and video clips were designed and developed to help teachers and students enhance teaching and learning process.

A quantitative research design was used specifically, the research and development design

to determine the acceptability level of 30 grade 7 MAPEH teachers teaching in public schools in Koronadal City Division and 267 grade 7 students of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips.

A survey questionnaire adopted from SKSU IMDC was employed to evaluate the said instructional materials. Mean was used to determine the acceptability level of teachers and students to the developed LYKA lesson examples and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package. Moreover, t-test was employed to compute its significant difference between the acceptability level of teachers and students.

The results highlighted that the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips achieved a very high extent result in all content, organization, mechanics, and overall package indicators both for grade 7 MAPEH teachers with an overall mean of 4.75 (SD= 0.45) and for grade 7 students with an overall mean of 4.58 (S=0.76). Overall, it met 91-100% of quality expectations. Therefore,

the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips were accepted by the teachers and students as useful tools to improve the quality basic education and foster 21st century skills for PE and Health MATATAG Curriculum.

A t-test value of 5.93 and a p-value of 0.00 shows that the difference is statistically significant because the p-value (0.00) is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the acceptability

level of grade 7 MAPEH teachers and grade students to the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package. The results found that, there were meaningful variations or preference in how teachers and students perceived the quality, usefulness, or appeal of the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips. On the other hand, the instructional materials can be useful for teachers and students to achieve and enhance teaching and learning.

Keywords: *MATATAG Curriculum, Lesson Exemplars, Video Clips, Physical Education, Health, Content, Organization, Mechanics, Overall Package*

INTRODUCTION

One role of teachers is to provide students with quality education through effective teaching. Effective learning and teaching can be achieved through the combination of a learning environment, an effective curriculum, quality teaching methods, motivation, and efficient learning resources. As an educator in the Philippines, the researcher's personal experience and observation show that teachers still face challenges in quality teaching, including the alignment of curriculum with global demand, learning crisis, unavailability of facilities, equipment, and insufficient teaching and learning resources.

In the Philippine context, a new curriculum was implemented under DepEd Order No. 10, series of 2024, also known as the MATATAG curriculum. This revised curriculum was a response to the issues and challenges faced by the Philippines' educational system, including the low performance in PISA (2022) and the 18.9 million data for functionally illiterate Filipinos who completed secondary education between 2019 and 2024. Some factors include overcrowded classrooms, insufficient resources, teacher shortages, numerous content areas, misplaced prerequisite competencies, and imbalances in thinking demands (Estrellado, 2024).

Aside from the curriculum, efficient and quality teaching and learning materials should be emphasized. In the MATATAG Curriculum, teachers use lesson exemplars as instructional materials. Using lesson exemplars as a teaching and learning technique is essential in helping students become more capable of making evaluations and working collaboratively with peers. Lesson exemplars have been utilized to enhance students' knowledge and skills. Therefore, without a lesson exemplar, a teacher lacks a clear outline of the topics, which has a negative impact on students (Hawe et al., 2017).

However, in the implementation of the MATATAG curriculum, various issues have been discovered. One of the challenges expressed by teachers is the insufficient availability of learning resources and materials (Loza, 2024), teacher readiness, lack of access to information resources, and infrastructural challenges (Kilag, 2024). In addition, Garma's (2024) study revealed that teachers were discouraged because of the unavailability of instructional materials, which were not suitable for all kinds of students

As an MAPEH teacher in the DepEd, I witnessed and personally observed the struggles of teachers in collecting and finding reliable sources, such as lesson exemplars, especially as they adjusted to the new curriculum. Furthermore, some teachers struggle to visualize their lessons, including sample pictures, videos, skills, and achievable activities.

To address this timely and relevant difficulty for teachers and students, the researcher developed simple yet abundant teaching and learning materials to serve as a supplemental source to address the concerns. The LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were available in print and online for easy access. These products can help teachers reduce their work and enhance teaching through activities, strategies, assessments, and resources. At the same time, to improve the quality of education, strengthen skills, and shape values.

Additionally, it has video clips that serve as an additional resource to help teachers demonstrate learning to students. At the same time, the students can review, rewatch, and confirm their learning with a video clip given by the teacher. It provides students with a clearer picture and is convenient to use. Teachers can adopt or use the validated and evaluated LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in their classes especially in implementing the new curriculum. Moreover, the researcher believed that this study could greatly help teachers, students, and the education sector.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to design and develop LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips for PE and Health 7 under MATATAG Curriculum. Specifically, to answer the following questions:

1. What is the acceptability level of teachers to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. organization;
 - 1.3. mechanics; and
 - 1.4. overall package?
2. What is the acceptability level of students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of:
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. organization;
 - 2.3. mechanics; and,
 - 2.4. overall package?
3. Is there no significant difference between the acceptability level of teachers and students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package?

METHODS

The study utilized a quantitative type of research, specifically a research and development (R&D) design to determine the acceptability level of grade 7 MAPEH teachers and grade 7 students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package. Moreover, a descriptive method was used to collect numerical data to describe the results of the evaluated LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips.

The study was conducted in Koronadal City, specifically among grade 7 MAPEH teachers teaching in public schools within Koronadal City Division and among grade 7 students of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School.

The developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were validated by the experts and evaluated by the respondents of this study, who were the (30) grade 7 MAPEH teachers teaching in public schools in Koronadal City Division and (267) grade 7 students of Koronadal National Comprehensive High School enrolled in the school year 2024-2025.

This study used a purposive sampling technique for the grade 7 MAPEH teachers as evaluators of the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips specifically the homogeneous sampling was employed. Relative to this, the grade 7 MAPEH teachers teaching in public schools in Koronadal City were directly applicable to this specific group. They shared the same or similar characteristics such as teachers specializing in PE/MAPEH, teaching on the same grade level, teaching the same subjects which is PE and Health, and underwent similar training for the MATATAG curriculum. On the other hand, the grade 7 students were identified as respondents by the simple random sampling technique through a lottery to be the evaluators also of the said products.

This study employed questionnaire through survey. The validation form was given to the expert validators who assessed, evaluated, and validated the instructional materials. The same applied to teachers and students-respondents who were given evaluation tools to assess the learning materials regarding a.) content, b.) organization, c.) mechanics, and d.) overall package. The evaluation tool was adopted from the Sultan Kudarat State University Instructional Materials Development Center (IMDC).

Mean was used to determine the level of acceptability of the grade 7 MAPEH teachers and grade 7 students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and the overall package. Moreover, a t-test was employed to compute the significant difference between the acceptability level of teachers and students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package. The five-point Likert scale was adopted from Sultan Kudarat State University IMDC to measure the quality and acceptability of LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in teaching Grade 7 PE and Health Matatag Curriculum.

RESULTS

Table 2. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 MAPEH Teachers to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Content

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1	Coverage of the lesson	4.97	0.18	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Appropriateness of the activities/exercises	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Appropriateness of the language used	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Content is appropriate to the target age level	4.80	0.41	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

5	Content is culture-sensitive	4.63	0.49	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Content is gender sensitive	4.77	0.43	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Exercises/activities are by the Filipino Values	4.97	0.18	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Illustration and content are by ethical standards	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Explanations are self-explanatory	4.87	0.35	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.86	0.35	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The findings indicate the teachers' evaluation in terms of content. It showed that all content indicators received an overall mean of 4.86 (SD=0.35), indicating a Very High Extent result. Specifically, the coverage of the lesson (M= 4.97, SD=0.18), appropriateness of the activities/exercises (M= 4.90, SD=0.31), appropriateness of the language used (M= 4.90, SD=0.31), content is appropriate to the target age level (M= 4.80, SD=0.41), content is culture (M= 4.97, SD=0.49) and gender-sensitive (M= 4.97, SD=0.43), exercises/activities are by the Filipino values (M= 4.97, SD=0.18), illustration and content are by ethical standards (M= 4.90, SD=0.31), and explanations are self-explanatory (M= 4.87, SD=0.35). It met the 91-100% of the quality expectations which means that the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips were excellent quality content, well-structured, and appropriate to students' needs.

Furthermore, among the content indicators, both indicators 1 and 7 got the highest mean of 4.97 (SD=0.18), expressing that the LYKA covered all the PE and Health 7 lessons and obtained Filipino values through the activities. On the other hand, indicator 5 gained a lowest mean of 4.63 (SD=0.49), though still it rated at a Very High Extent. This means that the content of instructional materials should observe culture sensitivity for inclusivity and equality.

The results align with Sadiq and Zamir's (2014) study, which stated that quality teaching materials should be precise, clear, relevant, and standard-compliant. Guido (2014) added the significance of content in developing instructional materials. The content must be based on the student's needs, skills, level, cultural background, and the lessons must be sufficient. Additionally, Harsono (2015) recommended that the primary goal of developing instructional material is to stimulate students' curiosity so they can learn independently.

Table 3. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 MAPEH Teachers to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Organization

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1	Sequence of topics (simple to complex)	4.83	0.38	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

2	Order of presentation of the lesson	4.97	0.18	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Arrangement of basic parts	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Illustration used	4.40	0.56	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Spacing of every part	4.77	0.43	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Harmony of the font styles	4.60	0.50	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Uniformity of layout	4.63	0.49	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Technical Description (Objective per lesson)	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Technical terms used	4.67	0.48	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Concepts of every lesson	4.73	0.45	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.74	0.45	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The findings show the teachers' evaluation of the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of organization. Based on the table, all organization indicators achieved a Very High Extent results, such as sequence of topics (simple to complex) ($M= 4.83$, $SD=0.38$), order of presentation of the lesson ($M= 4.97$, $SD= 0.18$), arrangement of basic parts ($M= 4.90$, $SD=0.31$), illustration used ($M= 4.40$, $SD=0.56$), spacing of every part ($M= 4.77$, $SD=0.43$), harmony of the font styles ($M= 4.60$, $SD=0.50$), uniformity of layout ($M= 4.63$, $SD=0.49$), technical description (Objective per lesson) ($M= 4.90$, $SD=0.31$), technical terms used ($M= 4.67$, $SD=0.48$), and concepts of every lesson ($M= 4.73$, $SD=0.45$) with an overall mean of 4.74 ($SD=0.45$). The result means that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips met 91-100% of the quality expectations in which everything was in order, clear, organized, and consistent to use.

Furthermore, among the organization indicators, indicator 2 received the highest mean of 4.97 ($SD=0.18$), which means that the lesson presentation was in order while indicator 4 got the lowest mean of 4.40 ($SD=0.56$), reflecting that the instructional materials' organization should improve its illustrations. Illustrations should be clear, relevant, and visually appealing.

The findings indicated that a well-designed material enhances students' abilities and opportunities to master the topics. It sequentially teaches concepts, allowing students to concentrate on their particular skills (Manalastas & De Leon, 2021). In addition, the organization and illustrations were significant in developing students' school performance, as supported by the study of Gustiani et al. (2017).

Table 4. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 MAPEH Teachers to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Mechanics

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1	General instruction is user-friendly	4.70	0.47	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Examples are coherent	4.77	0.43	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Font size is readable	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	A step-by-step procedure is in order	4.87	0.35	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Arrangement of parts	4.67	0.48	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Clarity images /pictures/ graphs/videos	4.33	0.61	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Individual differences are considered per activity	4.37	0.61	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Weaknesses of target users are considered	4.50	0.51	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Development of one's creativity and critical thinking (assets) are emphasized	4.77	0.43	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Clear instruction per activity	4.63	0.49	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.65	0.51	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The table indicates the teachers' evaluation to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of mechanics. It revealed an overall of 4.65 (SD=0.51), indicating a Very High Extent result.

Indicators were general instruction is user-friendly ($M= 4.704$, $SD=0.47$), examples are coherent ($M= 4.77$, $SD=0.43$), font size is readable ($M= 4.90$, $SD=0.31$), step-by-step procedure is in order ($M= 4.87$, $SD=0.35$), arrangement of parts ($M= 4.67$, $SD=0.48$), clarity of images/pictures/graphs/videos ($M= 4.33$, $SD=0.61$), individual differences are considered per activity ($M= 4.37$, $SD=0.61$), weaknesses of target users are considered ($M= 4.50$, $SD=0.51$), development of one's creativity and critical thinking (assets) are emphasized ($M= 4.77$, $SD=0.43$), and clear instruction per activity ($M= 4.63$, $SD=0.49$). It means it met the 91-100% of the quality expectations regarding mechanics. The result shows that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were friendly, accessible to diverse students, well-structured and well-designed instructional materials.

Additionally, indicator 3 got the highest mean of 4.90 ($SD=0.31$). It shows that the teachers could read all the letters and words easily. However, the teachers evaluated the indicator 6 with the lowest mean of 4.33 ($SD=0.61$) which means to give emphasis to the clarity of images/pictures/graphs/videos for visual appeal and coherence.

These findings align with the study of Guido (2014), which emphasized the use of simple, understandable language and clear concepts. Similarly, it was discovered by the study of Halamish et al., (2018) that when using font size for learning, children and adults can recall words with a larger front size more easily than with a smaller one. Large font words have a memory benefit, according to a new meta-analysis study. Conceicao et al. (2007) study, discussed that the students' positive behaviors and activities toward learning materials are influenced by how resources are presented and their visual attractiveness. Overall, readability is determined by the language and style. In addition, multimedia components—text, images, music, video, and animation—help the teaching and learning process interactively (Akinoson, 2018).

Table 5. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 MAPEH Teachers to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Overall Package

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1	Styles of letter fonts	4.97	0.18	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Appropriateness of binding techniques used	4.83	0.38	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Paper size used	4.87	0.35	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Paper quality used	4.90	0.31	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Color combinations	4.30	0.65	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Durability	4.77	0.43	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

7	Handiness	4.73	0.45	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Appropriateness of cover design	4.57	0.50	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Usability	4.93	0.25	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Labels and captions	4.57	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.74	0.47	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

It shows the teachers' evaluation to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of overall package with an overall mean of 4.74 (SD= 0.47), showing a Very High Extent result specifically the styles of letter fonts (M= 4.97, SD=0.18), appropriateness of binding techniques used (M= 4.83, SD=0.38), paper size used (M= 4.87, SD=0.35), paper quality used (M= 4.90, SD=0.31), color combinations (M= 4.30, SD=0.65), durability (M= 4.77, SD=0.43), handiness (M= 4.73, SD=0.45), appropriateness of cover design (M= 4.57, SD=0.50), usability (M= 4.93, SD=0.25), and labels and captions (M= 4.57, SD=0.57). The result indicates that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were well-designed, quality, and suitable for educational use.

Among the overall package indicators, indicator 1 obtained a highest mean of 4.97 (SD=0.18), indicating that the letter font style used was excellent. On the other hand, the color combination indicator rated the lowest mean of 4.30 (SD=0.65), implying that the instructional materials must improve the colors used.

To guarantee a positive student experience, it can also be connected to other elements like readability, accessibility, and findability (Rubin et al., 2008). The main medium for communicating ideas is through text or letters. Text on displays must be readable in order to guarantee successful engagement and raise teachers and students reading ability (Hojjati & Muniand, 2014). Additionally, for word processing, Bernard et al. (2001) stressed that Arial is frequently selected as font styles. The study by Cerbo (2024) found that the design, layout, visual appeal, and user-friendliness improved the learning experience.

Table 6. Summary of Teachers' Level of Acceptance to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Content	4.86	0.35	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Organization	4.74	0.45	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

Mechanics	4.65	0.51	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Package	4.74	0.47	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean	4.75	0.45	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The findings in Table 7 indicate that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips achieved an overall mean rating of 4.75 (SD= 0.45), expressing a Very High Extent result which met the 91-100% of the quality expectations. Therefore, all the teachers accepted LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips regarding content, organization, mechanics, and overall package. The result proved that LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were great for quality teaching and learning.

Among the indicators, the content gained the highest mean rating of 4.86 (SD= 0.35), expressing content, lesson, and activities appropriate to the target grade 7 learners and teachers. This finding is backed by the study of Rillorta (2021) that instructional materials give the core information or content for the teachers and students to learn and experience. It should correspond to the curriculum, involving the learning objectives, activities, and assessment. Bacio and Sagge (2019) added that, which found that instructional materials may be appropriate for their target users if the objectives, content, activities, and assessment are sufficient.

Based on the results, all these indicators must be highlighted to raise engagement and better learning outcomes. Lopez et al. (2021), stressed out the clear and well-structured instructional materials can enhance critical thinking, creativity, and improve learning.

Table 7. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Students to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Content

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal description	Interpretation
1	Coverage of the lesson	4.67	0.54	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Appropriateness of the activities/exercises	4.67	0.54	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Appropriateness of the language used	4.68	0.61	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Content is appropriate to the target age level	4.65	0.62	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Content is culture-sensitive	4.50	0.77	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

6	Content is gender sensitive	4.50	0.79	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Exercises/activities are by the Filipino Values	4.62	0.60	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Illustration and content are by ethical standards	4.54	0.60	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Explanations are self-explanatory	4.43	0.74	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.58	0.66	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The table displays the evaluation of students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content. It exhibited that all content indicators achieved a Very High Extent result with an overall mean of 4.58 (SD=0.66). Specifically, the coverage of the lesson (M= 4.67, SD=0.54), appropriateness of the activities/exercises (M= 4.67, SD=0.54), appropriateness of the language used (M= 4.68, SD=0.61), content is appropriate to the target age level (M= 4.65, SD=0.62), content is culture (M= 4.50, SD=0.77) and gender-sensitive (M= 4.50, SD=0.79), exercises/activities are by the Filipino values (M= 4.62, SD=0.60), illustration and content are by ethical standards (M= 4.54, SD=0.60). Explanations are self-explanatory (M= 4.43, SD=0.74). It implied that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips met 91-100% of the quality expectations in terms of content. The result presented well-made, well-structured, and efficient instructional materials aligned with the educational standards.

Furthermore, among the content indicators, indicator 3 got the highest mean of 4.68 (SD=0.61), indicating appropriate language used while indicator 9 got the lowest mean of 4.43 (SD=0.74). The result implied that the instructional materials should be more self-explanatory to students.

Appropriate language used is vital for good communication (M_ishtiaq_fi, 2012). Salazar (2018) indicated that material clarity needs to be provided in clear information and language to aid learning. In developing materials, it should give the students chances to utilize the target language. In learning PE and Health, English is the appropriate language to use as English is our second language (Harsono, 2007). As per Roman's (2016) research, the content of the instructional materials must be aligned with the curriculum, and the contents play a role in determining the authenticity of the material. Salazar's study (2018) added that the contents of each lesson affect the most important aspects of what is being taught.

Table 8. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Students to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Organization

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal description	Interpretation
1	Sequence of topics (simple to complex)	4.61	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

2	Order of presentation of the lesson	4.62	0.63	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Arrangement of basic parts	4.66	0.61	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Illustration used	4.51	0.65	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Spacing of every part	4.44	0.67	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Harmony of the font styles	4.48	0.72	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Uniformity of layout	4.48	0.68	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Technical Description (Objective per lesson)	4.54	0.63	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Technical terms used	4.56	0.64	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Concepts of every lesson	4.70	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.56	0.64	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

Table shows the students' evaluation of the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of organization. It achieved a Very High Extent result with an overall mean of 4.56 (SD=0.64) it means, it met 91-100% of the quality expectations. Specifically, sequence of topics (simple to complex) (M= 4.61, SD=0.57), order of presentation of the lesson (M= 4.62, SD=0.63), arrangement of basic parts (M= 4.66, SD=0.61), the illustration used (M= 4.51, SD=0.65), spacing of every part (M= 4.44, SD=0.67), the harmony of the font styles (M= 4.48, SD=0.72), uniformity of layout (M= 4.48, SD=0.68), technical description (Objective per lesson) (M= 4.54, SD=0.63), technical terms used (M= 4.56, SD=0.64), and concepts of every lesson (M= 4.70, SD=0.57). The result showed that LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were well-organized, ordered, cleared objectives, and concepts.

In addition, indicator 10 got the highest mean of 4.70 (SD=0.57), demonstrating concepts of every lesson. On the other hand, indicator 5 had the lowest mean of 4.44 (SD=0.67) referring to the spacing of every part that must be observed to easily read and comprehend the instructional materials.

The student's learning capacity must be considered when developing the instructional materials in understandable concepts, ideas, and structure (Saludo & Nabos, 2023). Another is to organize logically based on subjects, from simple to complex concepts (Gaestimos, 2015).

Table 9. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Students to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Mechanics.

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal description	Interpretation
1	General instruction is user-friendly	4.73	0.51	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Examples are coherent	4.58	0.64	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Font size is readable	4.75	0.56	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	A step-by-step procedure is in order	4.67	0.61	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Arrangement of parts	4.64	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Clarity images/pictures/graphs/videos	4.50	0.66	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Individual differences are considered per activity	4.45	0.71	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Weaknesses of target users are considered	4.34	0.78	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Development of one's creativity and critical thinking (assets) are emphasized	4.50	0.65	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Clear instruction per activity	4.73	0.51	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Mean		4.59	1.01	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The finding presents the student's evaluation to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of Mechanics. It exhibited an overall mean of 4.59 (SD= 0.01), expressing a Very High Extent result. Some indicators are general instruction is user-friendly (M= 4.73, SD= 0.51), examples are coherent (M= 4.58, SD= 0.64), font size is readable (M= 4.75, SD= 0.56), a step-by-step procedure is in order (M= 4.67, SD= 0.61), arrangement of parts (M= 4.64, SD= 0.57), clarity of images/pictures/graphs/videos (M= 4.50, SD= 0.66), individual differences are considered per activity (M= 4.45, SD= 0.71), weaknesses of target users are considered (M= 4.34, SD= 0.78), development of one's creativity and critical thinking (assets) are emphasized (M= 4.50, SD= 0.65), and clear instruction per activity (M= 4.73, SD= 0.51). With

this, the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips met 91-100% of the quality expectations regarding mechanics.

Indicator 3 got the highest mean of 4.75 (SD=0.56), indicating that the students can read all the letters and words easily. However, indicator 8 received the lowest rate of 4.34 (SD=0.78), exhibiting on considering target users' weaknesses. This implied to address the learners' difficulties and challenges to the lesson and activities.

The results align with Tavakoli and Kheirzadeh (2011) study, who emphasized that font size improves reading speed. Moreover, Namaska et al. (2017) said that easy-to-use instructional material, appropriate to target learners and good layouts can develop quality teaching and learning. Vergara's (2017) study, which stated that the efficiency and uniformity of instructional materials are guaranteed if the material follows a good sequence. Carney and Levin (2002) revealed in their study that pictures and designs are important in demonstrating information and assisting students' learning, which is why a well-planned concept of designs must be maximized.

Table 10. Acceptability Level of Grade 7 Students to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in Terms of Overall Package

No.	Characteristics/ Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal description	Interpretation
1	Styles of letter of fonts	4.54	0.66	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
2	Appropriateness of binding techniques used	4.64	0.56	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
3	Paper size used	4.68	0.56	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
4	Paper quality used	4.67	0.62	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
5	Color combinations	4.45	0.68	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
6	Durability	4.45	0.71	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
7	Handiness	4.41	0.75	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
8	Appropriateness of cover design	4.49	0.68	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
9	Usability	4.72	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
10	Labels and captions	4.57	0.57	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

Overall Mean	4.58	0.65	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
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It displays the overall weighted mean of 4.58 (SD=0.65) from students' evaluation to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of overall package, exhibiting a Very High Extent result. It met the 91-100% of the quality expectations specifically the styles of letter fonts (M= 4.54, SD=0.66), appropriateness of binding techniques used (M= 4.64, SD=0.56), paper size used (M= 4.68, SD=0.56), paper quality used (M= 4.67, SD=0.62), color combinations (M= 4.45, SD=0.68), durability (M= 4.45, SD=0.71), handiness (M= 4.41, SD=0.75), appropriateness of cover design (M= 4.49, SD=0.68), usability (M= 4.72, SD=0.57), and labels and captions (M= 4.57, SD=0.57). The result showed that the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were well-designed and suitable for educational use.

Based on the data presented, among the overall package indicators, indicator 9 received the highest mean of 4.72 (SD=0.57), showing that the instructional materials were useful to students in learning the subject. Conversely, indicator 7, handiness rated as the lowest mean of 4.41 (SD=0.75). With this, the instructional materials must be handy and light duty to students.

The findings reveal that in developing learning instructional material, usability is essential because it can determine whether a task is completed precisely or not (Goode, 2003). Shulman's (2020) study emphasized that student's motivation and retention are increased by a well-structured module with proper binding, clear formatting, and readability. Furthermore, Tomlinson's (2017) discussed how to improve students' engagement and learning outcomes, resources should be high quality, durable, aesthetically pleasing, and user-friendly.

Table 11. Summary of Students' Level of Acceptance to LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal description	Interpretation
Content	4.58	0.66	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Organization	4.56	0.64	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Mechanics	4.59	1.01	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall Package	4.58	0.65	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations
Overall	4.58	0.76	Very high extent	Meets 91-100% of the quality expectations

The finding presents the students' acceptance to LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips with an overall mean of 4.58 (SD=0.76), indicating a Very High Extent result which met the 91-100% of the quality expectations. Therefore, all the students accepted the instructional material in terms of content,

organization, mechanics, and overall package. The result proved that LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips were great tool use for quality learning.

Based to the findings, mechanics got the highest mean of 4.59 (SD=1.01). Hernandez and Gonzalez's (2020) study highlighted how student engagement and comprehension are enhanced by well-structured, clear mechanics instructional materials. In contrast, the organization indicator received the lowest mean rating of 4.56 (SD=0.64). The table dictates that sequence and order of presentation must be observed.

Funa (2019) believed that learning materials and student understanding must align. It should provide up-to-date, reliable, and legitimate examples that complement curriculum standards and learning objectives. In addition, the study by Liu et al. (2018) revealed that well-designed instructional materials containing all elements and teaching components resulted in quality and effective learning.

Table 12. Independent T-Test Between the Acceptability Level of Teachers and Students to the Developed LYKA Lesson Exemplars and Video Clips in terms of Content, Organization, Mechanics, and Overall Package

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Teacher	30	4.75	0.11	5.93	0.00	significant	Reject Ho
Students	267	4.58	0.31				

It displays the acceptability level of teachers and students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package.

Based on table 13, the acceptability level of teachers to the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and overall package resulted to an overall mean of 4.75 (SD=0.11) while the students' acceptability level to the same instructional materials got an overall mean of 4.58 (SD=0.31).

A t-test value of 5.93 and a p-value of 0.00 shows that the difference is statistically significant because the p-value (0.00) is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, there was a significant difference in the acceptability of the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips between the teachers and students. The results found that, there were meaningful variations or preference in how teachers and students perceived the quality, usefulness, or appeal of the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips.

Generally, the findings indicate that teachers and students have different views and perceptions in terms of instructional materials. Teachers tend to have a more positive perception, particularly when it comes to digital resources and visual aids while the students frequently view instructional materials as a source of interaction and motivation. Student learning styles, curricular expectations, and teaching experiences are some of the causes of these differences (Wang et al., 2021).

In addition, the instructional materials can be useful and used by teachers and students to achieve quality education. The result means that instructional materials have complete ingredients of learning objectives, strategies, activities, and evaluation (Donnelly & Fitzmaurice, 2005). Lamas et al. (2016) added that the material should be designed and developed with appropriate and effective teaching pedagogies and instructional resources to maximize teaching and learning progress. Similarly, the material can elevate the students' retention, critical thinking, problem-solving capabilities, and skills and help the teachers provide quality teaching (DeCaporale-Ryan et al., 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendation

The evaluation of the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips based on its content, organization, mechanics, and overall package, resulted in a very high extent both for teachers and students. It both showed excellent quality expectations. It means that grade 7 MAPEH teachers and grade 7 students accepted the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips as useful and helpful instructional materials to enhance teaching and learning process.

On the other hand, based on the t-test result, it showed that there was a significant difference between the acceptability level of teachers and students to the developed LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips. The results found that there were meaningful variations or preferences on how teachers and students perceived the quality, usefulness, and appearance of the LYKA lesson exemplar and video clips.

Based on the findings, the following recommendation were made:

1. The developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips are recommended to use by the MAPEH teachers specifically in grade 7 to achieve quality instruction and relevant learning.
2. The Grade 7 MAPEH teachers can let the students access the video clips and activities for additional guidance.
3. The students can use the learning activities and view the video clips uploaded on researcher's YouTube channel for additional learning.
4. The school/administration can adopt or use the LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips as supplementary sources in teaching Grade 7 PE and Health under the MATATAG Curriculum.
5. The study can be used to test the effectiveness of the developed LYKA lesson exemplars and video clips for grade 7 PE and Health MATATAG Curriculum.
6. Another study could be conducted related to this study to further improve the instructional materials.

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